

CARBOXYMETHYLATION OF CELLULOSE OBTAINED FROM AGRICULTURAL RESIDUES

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Abstract: *We have focused on the residual biomass, which is especially abundant in Slovenia and originates from corn and wheat harvesting. First, we chemically characterized typical biomass, such as corn stover, corn stems and peeled cobs as well as wheat straw. We determined the contents of cellulose, lignin, hemicellulose, extractives and ash. Due to the relatively high portions of cellulose in representative samples, which were between 35% and 44%, the materials were further on delignified by alkaline procedure using NaOH as reagent. Isolated cellulose fibers were analyzed for mechanical, morphological and other properties. At the same time, we optimized the delignification process to find out how the delignification conditions affect the properties of the isolated cellulose fibers. In addition, we studied the conversion of isolated cellulose fibers into the carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) by Williamson ether synthesis in various solvents and under different experimental conditions. CMC synthesis was performed on cellulose fibers isolated from corn stover, corn stems and peeled cobs as well as wheat straw. We also examined possible differences in CMC synthesis while using native (cellulose I) and regenerated cellulose (cellulose II) as starting materials.*

Keywords: agricultural residues, delignification process, cellulose, Williamson ether synthesis, carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC)

1 INTRODUCTION

Large quantities of stem biomass are generated after annual harvesting of cereal crops, however the latter are usually not optimally utilized. In some cases farmers use these agricultural residues as animal feed and litter, but in most cases they are left behind on the fields or else they are composted or simply burnt. The increasing environmental concerns caused by modern industry have led us to consider possible technological utilization of agricultural residues to produce added value products. Among others, this kind of biomass is very usable in the paper industry and subsequently also for packaging. The plant biomass consists predominantly of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin (Iglič, 1988), of which the most important are cellulose fibers. Cellulose is a linear and high molecular weight macromolecule in which glucose monosaccharide units are linked by β -1,4-glycosidic bonds (Hon and Shiraishi, 2001). Cellulose is considered by many to be the most abundant polymer on Earth, or even the most abundant organic matter on Earth. It can be modified to many useful chemical feedstocks, such as cellulose ethers and esters (Klemm et al, 1998). One of the most important cellulose derivatives is CMC. It is a linear, long-chain, water-soluble polysaccharide having quite high viscosity and polyelectrolyte character so it can be used for applications in the textile, food, paper and pharmaceutical industries (Singh and Singh, 2013).

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2. 1 Biomass samples

Corn stover, stems and peeled cobs; wheat straw.

2. 2 Chemical characterization of biomass

Prior to chemical analyses the representative biomass samples were ground to 0.5 mm sieved particles. The determination of cellulose was carried out by Kürschner-Hoffer method (Kürschner and Hoffer, 1931), hemicellulose by chlorite method (Wise, Murphy and D'Addieco, 1946), lignin by Klason's method (TAPPI T 222 om 02), ash by standard method TAPPI T 211 om-93 and extractives by standard method TAPPI T 204 cm 97.

2. 3 Delignification process

First, we cut the biomass into smaller pieces. The delignification process was carried out at 160 °C and elevated pressure in a 5 L laboratory delignificator using 18% NaOH solution as reagent (18% represents the proportion of NaOH

relative to the amount of absolutely dry biomass). Mass ratio of absolutely dry biomass to water was 1:5. The delignification reaction lasted 3 hours and after process optimization 1.5 hours. When the process was completed, neutralization, disintegration, screening, squeezing and homogenization took place.

2. 4 Determination of mechanical and morphological properties

Mechanical properties were measured from laboratory sheets which were prepared according to ISO 5269-2. Breaking length was determined according to ISO 1924-2. Average fiber length and width were determined on Valmet Fiber Image Analyser FS5 from dilute fiber suspensions.

2. 5 Determination of lignin content in isolated cellulose fibers (Kappa number)

This parameter was determined according to the international standard method ISO 302:2015(E).

2. 6 Synthesis of CMC

Syntheses were performed in different solvents, such as isopropanol, ethanol and HFIP (1,1,1,3,3,3-hexafluoro-2-propanol). For all reactions, 2.55 mmol NaOH mmol⁻¹ AGU (in the case of in situ formation of sodium chloroacetate 5.1 mmol NaOH mmol⁻¹ AGU) and 2.04 mmol sodium chloroacetate mmol⁻¹ AGU or 2.04 mmol chloroacetic acid mmol⁻¹ AGU were used. First, we performed alkalization process using 4 mL of pure solvent, cellulose pulp (the mass of absolutely dry matter was 81 mg) and 1.275 mmol NaOH. In the case of isopropanol as solvent, about 100 µL of distilled water was added to the solution to accelerate the dissolution of NaOH. The reaction was carried out for 1 hour at a temperature of 25 °C to 40 °C. This was followed by the etherification process with 1.02 mmol sodium chloroacetate or chloroacetic acid (in this case, we also added 1.275 mmol NaOH to the solution), which was mixed in advance with 2 ml pure solvent and about 400 µL distilled water and added to previous solution. The etherification was performed from 1 hour to 23 hours at a temperature of 60 °C to 75 °C. Finally, we added an excess of acetic acid to the solution, filtered off the solid residue, washed with 70% methanol and dried at 100 °C to constant weight.

2. 7 Additional analyses

Additional analyzes of isolated cellulose fibers and CMC cellulose fibers were performed with FTIR spectroscopy (FTIR spectra were recorded on Bruker FTIR Alpha Platinum ATR and Spectrum Two PerkinElmer). Microscopic images were

obtained on the Nikon Eclipse 80i optical microscope and SEM images on scanning electron microscope Thermo Fisher Scientific Quattro S. We also used commercial cellulose fibers as reference cellulose in the course of Williamson ether synthesis and compared the obtained FTIR spectra with FTIR spectra of a commercial CMC, where the degree of substitution (DS) was determined using the Eyrer method (Eyrer, Klug and Diephuis, 1947).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of biomass characterization have shown that the materials (corn stover, corn stems and peeled cobs as well as wheat straw) consist of relatively different percentages of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. The contents of cellulose and lignin depend on the character of biomass. Therefore, in the case of wood biomass, the content of these two components is higher than in the case of agricultural biomass (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Composition of biomass

As the Figure 1 indicates, the cellulose content was quite high in all cases, so we decided to isolate it by delignification process, which is used for breaking down the chemical structure of lignin and rendering it soluble in a liquid. The properties of isolated cellulose fibers varied from sample to sample. In the case of peeled corn cobs, no cellulose fibers were obtained as a result of delignification. In fact, only very small cellulose fragments were generated (Figure 2a). Scanning electron microscopy revealed interesting shapes of cellulose fibers (Figures 2b, 2c, 2d and 2e). Optical microscopy revealed the presence of different cells, such as trachea, parenchymal and epidermal cells (Karlsson, 2006) (Figure 2f).

Figure 2: SEM and optical microscopic images of isolated cellulose fibers

The results have shown that the properties of cellulose fibers, in particular the breaking length as the most representative mechanical property, greatly depend on the conditions of the delignification process. Therefore, the longer the delignification process is, the smaller the lignin content of fibers is and the lower the values of mechanical parameters are. On the other hand, the morphological properties of fibers are much less dependent on the delignification conditions (Table 1).

Table 1: Dependence of the properties of cellulose fibers isolated from wheat straw on the conditions of delignification process

Property	Value at 3 h delignification	Value at 1.5 h delignification
Breaking length [m]	3530	5575
Fiber length (L_c (I) ISO) [mm]	0.697	0.808
Fiber width [μm]	15.27	15.72
Kappa number	8	16

We also checked the applicability of isolated cellulose fibers for the modification process. Thus, we conducted the synthesis of CMC by Williamson ether reaction. The results have shown that the course of the reaction depends on the solvent in which the reaction takes place (Figure 3). Namely, it turned out that such reactions proceeded well in ethanol and isopropanol under the conditions that are described in section Experimental, but rather poorly in HFIP. On the other hand, the course of the reaction does not very depend on whether or not regenerated cellulose (cellulose II) is used except when the NaOH concentration in the alkalization process is high (Ambjörnsson, Schenzel and Germgård, 2013). Cellulose II is obtained when cellulose I is stirred between 0.5 and 1 hour in 18% NaOH solution at room temperature. So, it is

feasible to use native cellulose (cellulose I) without any pre-treatment process when performing such reactions.

Figure 3: FTIR spectra of the products obtained in synthesis of CMC in isopropanol (black FTIR spectrum), ethanol (red FTIR spectrum) and HFIP (green FTIR spectrum) using cellulose fibers isolated from wheat straw (alkalization process was carried out at 40 °C for 1 hour and etherification at 70 °C for 7 hours)

Further research has shown that CMC is formed after a short time of performing etherification step, so for example, this process can be carried out only for 1 hour. Of course, the FTIR spectrum of CMC differs considerably if we perform the etherification process for less or more time, which indicates that the degree of substitution and other properties of CMC vary with the time of implementation of both stages of Williamson ether synthesis. The degree of substitution and other properties of CMC are also quite dependent on other conditions under which CMC synthesis takes place (e.g. concentration of reagents, temperatures at which both stages take place, ...). In addition to the aforementioned, the results have shown that the reactions of CMC formation on isolated cellulose fibers of different origin are quite similar despite the different mechanical, morphological and other properties. The resulting CMC products synthesized in different solvents differed in appearance, so we performed also analysis using scanning electron microscopy (Yanez-S et al, 2018). In the case of using isopropanol (Figure 4a), ethanol (Figure 4b) or HFIP (Figure 4c) as solvents, the cellulose fibers form different structures, which is reflected in their different properties. When CMC sodium salt was placed in water solutions, a rather viscous gel-like substance began to form (Figure 4d).

Figure 4: SEM microscopic images of CMC synthesized on the cellulose fibers isolated from corn stover

In the synthesis of CMC, it has also been established that there are some side reactions that could occur. Therefore, it is very important that CMC is well washed at the end of the synthesis with an aqueous alcohol solution, because the by-products are poorly soluble in anhydrous solutions.

4 CONCLUSION

It turned out that the cellulose, isolated from all the considered biomass samples is suitable for CMC synthesis. The latter can be used in the paper and packaging industries as efficient papermaking additive as well as for pigment coating and surface sizing of paper. Likewise, it can also be concluded that the cellulose fibers from these abundant agricultural residues may be also suitable for the preparation of other cellulose derivatives and composites. These agricultural residues with the exception of peeled corn cobs may be also conveniently applied in papermaking as alternative sources of high quality cellulose fibers.

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